

THE IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON WORKPLACE HAPPINESS AND PERFORMANCE: THE ROLES OF CORE SELF-EVALUATIONS, INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP, AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN PAKISTAN'S GARMENT SECTOR: A MULTIMEDIATOR-MODERATOR MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to find out the understanding of emotional intelligence, its importance in self-management and its impact on one's own well-being at work. Quantitative approaches were used as research methods. Using a structured research framework, data was collected from 150 HR professionals and analyzed using Smart PLS software. The theoretical framework of the thesis deals with emotional intelligence as a concept and its sub-areas, Inclusive leadership and Organizational Culture in Pakistan's Garment Sector. Emotional intelligence has been discussed through Goleman's emotional intelligence model, which includes five sub-areas, which are self-awareness, self-control, motivation, empathy and social skills. This is also related to emotional leadership and self-leadership from a leadership perspective, which are also discussed in the theory. The results of the study revealed that managers consider emotional skills and emotional intelligence to be particularly important management tools and utilize them in their work. Based on the study, it can be stated that emotional skills, such as empathy, are somewhat more natural to managers and they know how to utilize them in their work better than other managers.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Culture, Core Self-evaluations, Inclusive Leadership, Garment Sector, Workplace Happiness.

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

A contemporary workplace is becoming increasingly complex, requiring organizations to adapt to dynamic global demands while maintaining employee well-being and operational effectiveness. The role of human factors, particularly emotional and psychological elements, has gained prominence in shaping organizational success. Among these factors, Emotional Intelligence (EI) stands out as a key driver of individual and organizational outcomes. Emotional

intelligence refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and regulate one's own emotions, as well as the ability to perceive and influence the emotions of others (Leggat & Balding, 2013). Over the past two decades, researchers have established that EI plays a critical role in enhancing interpersonal relationships, improving decision-making processes, and fostering leadership effectiveness. Despite its growing significance, its application and impact within specific industries, such as the garment sector in Pakistan, remain

underexplored. The garment industry is one of Pakistan's largest and most labor-intensive sectors, contributing significantly to employment and export revenues. It employs millions of workers, predominantly from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, in environments often characterized by high job demands, stressful working conditions, and limited resources. These factors contribute to high employee turnover, reduced morale, and operational inefficiencies.

The garment industry in Pakistan is a cornerstone of economic growth and industrial employment, contributing substantially to the country's gross domestic product and export revenues. However, despite its economic significance, the industry faces persistent challenges that hinder its ability to ensure workplace well-being and achieve operational excellence. High levels of job stress, low job satisfaction, high turnover rates, and stagnant employee performance continue to plague the sector. These challenges are compounded by demanding production targets, limited resources, and stressful working environments characterized by repetitive tasks, long hours, and inadequate leadership (Walters-Salas, 2012).

Research Questions

1. How does emotional intelligence influence workplace well-being in the garment sector of Pakistan?
2. How do core self-evaluations mediate the relationship between emotional intelligence and workplace outcomes?
3. In what ways do organizational culture moderate the effects of emotional intelligence on workplace well-being and operational effectiveness?
4. How does inclusive leadership enhance the impact of emotional intelligence on workplace outcomes?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence

The concepts of feeling and intelligence are combined in emotional intelligence. Intelligence, in turn, has several definitions. The concept of emotional intelligence was created by Salovey & Mayer (1990) in an

attempt to distinguish between emotional and cognitive information processing. The concept of emotional intelligence became widely known in the 1990s through the book *Emotional Intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ* written by Abdullahi et al., (2020). Much of what influences our understanding of the effects of emotions on who we are, how we act, and how we relate to each other today is due to Goleman. Emotional intelligence is a relatively new concept and was until recently considered an alternative concept to social intelligence, in which people have the ability to understand others and act wisely in social situations. However, it is broader than this and includes not only feelings related to social relationships, but also internal feelings that are important for a person's personal growth. Beydler, (2017) found that emotional intelligence and general intelligence were separate phenomena and only very weakly positively correlated. The weak positive correlation between emotional intelligence and general intelligence was also noted by Krishnakumar et al., (2016), who found that they are connected to the same brain regions. The importance of inner feelings in emotional intelligence is emphasized by the differences between emotional intelligence and general intelligence in, for example, stress management. Riggio & Reichard, (2008) also found that higher emotional intelligence, but not general intelligence, predicted better stress tolerance in the studied individuals in everyday life. Emotional intelligence is connected to many positive phenomena. The research world has sought to investigate the connection between emotional intelligence and, for example, mind control, leadership, success at work and mental health. According to Duan et al., (2023), emotional intelligence refers to the ability to recognize, manage and process emotions in oneself and others. However, the scientific development of emotional intelligence and research into the concept have been found to be challenging. This is because there has been no consensus on the definition of the concept.

Goleman's Model of Emotional Intelligence

Daniel Goleman's (1995) original model of emotional intelligence consisted of emotional and social skills, which were divided into five different domains, and under these domains, Goleman placed 25 emotional intelligence abilities. Emotional intelligence is the skill of dealing with both oneself and other people. It is also based on the skill of being aware of one's own emotions and the skill of understanding the reasons that have given rise to these emotions. An individual must also distinguish between one's own emotions and actions and understand the significance of these differences. Controlling anger or the ability to express it appropriately is emotional management. For this reason, emotional intelligence is also important in leadership, as subordinates of leaders with deficient emotional skills have been found to be less motivated and committed than those of leaders with good emotional skills. According to Goleman (2009), one aspect of emotional intelligence is social intelligence. According to Goleman, social intelligence is caring for and caring for the needs of others, without forgetting present and focused listening. In a work community, the skill of perceiving nonverbal messages and the ability to put oneself in the other person's shoes is needed. According to Goleman, an individual who possesses these skills has instinctive empathy. The basis for the formation of empathy comes from the individual's understanding of the feelings of others and the ability to arouse mutual understanding. Empathy is one of the components of Goleman's original emotional intelligence model, in addition to self-awareness, motivation, self-control, and social skills.

The Model of Emotional Intelligence According to Bar-On

Psychologist Reuven Bar-On defines emotional intelligence as an emotional-social phenomenon through abilities, and this model of emotional intelligence is known as ESI (emotional social intelligence). According to Bar-On, a person's emotional and social abilities and skills determine how an individual understands and expresses themselves, how they understand and get

along with others, or cope with challenging everyday situations. Bar-On supports Goleman's research findings that emotional intelligence is a result of learning and that it is good to distinguish emotional intelligence from character traits and personality characteristics, because these are more permanent and unchanging than emotional intelligence throughout a person's life span. He has also developed, if not the best known, then at least the first emotional intelligence test, the EQ-i (emotional quotient inventory) (Koveshnikov et al., 2014). The theoretical basis of the test was born from Bar-On's social-emotional model of emotional intelligence in the 1980s and has received strong evidence of reliability and validity in the scientific community. By intrapersonal factors, Bar-On refers to an individual who is aware of their own internal emotional intelligence skills, i.e., awareness of their own emotions and who understands their strengths and weaknesses. In addition, the individual must be able to express their emotions. According to Bar-On, these intrapersonal factors in knowing one's own emotionally-socially intelligent.

Mayer and Salovey's Emotional Intelligence Ability Model

In their study of emotional intelligence, Salovey and Mayer (1990) sought to distinguish between emotional and cognitive information processing. They saw emotional intelligence as the ability to regulate emotions and solve problems based on them, but also as a mental ability in which an individual has the ability to recognize emotions and their meanings and connections in ourselves and others. Human personality is relatively stable, and Mayer and Salovey (1997) aimed to distinguish emotional intelligence from personality traits. They combined intelligence and emotions when defining emotional intelligence and stated that an emotionally intelligent person is aware of their own and others' emotions, and these emotions make the individual's thinking more intelligent, allowing them to regulate their own emotional reactions and thus positively affect the well-being of both themselves and the

people around them (Chignell, 2018). In 2002, Mayer and Salovey, together with their colleague Caruso, developed the MSCEIT test (The Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test) to measure emotional intelligence. Mayer and Salovey's ability model of emotional intelligence has been criticized as being too theoretical, but with the MSCEIT test, both Mayer and Salovey have been able to respond to the criticisms raised, and the test's scale has been found to be a valid measure of emotional intelligence in several studies.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for inspecting the effect of emotional intelligence (EI) on place of work happiness and performance integrates more than one mediating and moderating variables, which include center self-evaluations (CSEs), inclusive leadership, operational effectiveness, and organizational culture. Emotional intelligence, characterised by the ability to understand, apprehend, and

alter feelings, is a crucial determinant of workplace happiness and performance. Employees with excessive EI are better geared up to control interpersonal relationships, reduce place of work pressure, and beautify process pride, ultimately leading to improved productiveness and operational effectiveness. Core self-critiques (CSEs) serve as a key mediating factor in this dating. Comprising self-esteem, self-efficacy, emotional stability, and locus of control, CSEs affect employees' ability to make use of their emotional intelligence correctly (Bierema, 2016). Individuals with high CSEs exhibit confidence in their talents and resilience in the face of workplace demanding situations, making them more likely to enjoy happiness at work and a contribution undoubtedly to the organizational overall performance. In Pakistan's garment area, wherein personnel often face high-stress environments, the interplay between EI and CSEs plays a pivotal function in fostering workplace well-being.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses

- **H1:** Employees' emotional intelligence is positively related to happiness at work.
- **H2:** Employee emotional intelligence is positively related to core self-evaluations.
- **H3:** Core self-evaluations are positively related to happiness at work for employees.

- **H4:** Employees' emotional intelligence positively impacts inclusive leadership.
- **H5:** Inclusive leadership positively impacts operational effectiveness.
- **H6:** Organizational culture moderates the relationship between inclusive leadership and job performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

We have used **quantitative research method to measure and analyze our data**. It helps to test hypotheses, establish relationships, and generalize findings across large populations. Researchers typically use surveys, experiments, and observational methods to gather numerical data, and the results are often analyzed using statistical techniques to draw conclusions. While it offers objectivity, replicability, and precision, it is limited in providing deep contextual understanding compared to qualitative research.

Sampling Design

The research targeted HR professionals within the garment industry. The data is collected from HR managers, data analysts, and talent acquisition specialists of organizations. Our target population is 150. The data is also collected from employees of organizations who have information related to HR Analytics. We pre-tested our survey with HR professionals and incorporated their feedback. Data was collected through primary sources (Individuals and teams). There are approximately 150 garments in Pakistan. We have used simple Random Sampling Method. We have selected individuals randomly from garment industry including male and female both. The individuals are mainly from HR department. For Analysis of data we have used SEM technique. It is used to understand the relationship between the variables. Factor loading, average variance extracted (AVE), factor correlation values, and their descriptive statistics were used to assess the construct's convergent and discriminant validity. The composite reliability (CR) values were observed to test the reliability of our measurement.

Instrument

For this study, validated and widely used scales were employed to measure the key variables: Happiness at Work, Emotional Intelligence, Inclusive Leadership, Core Self-Evaluations, Organizational Culture, and Operational Effectiveness. Each variable was assessed using a multi-item scale, ensuring

reliability and validity in capturing the construct's essence.

1. Happiness at Work was measured using a 4-item scale adapted from Parker and Hyett (2011). This scale captures employees' perceptions of their well-being and energy levels at work. A sample item includes: "At my job, I feel strong and vigorous." The composite reliability (CR) of this scale was 0.91, indicating high internal consistency.
2. Emotional Intelligence was assessed using the Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS), which consists of 16 items. This scale evaluates individuals' ability to recognize, understand, and regulate emotions in themselves and others. A sample item is: "I am sensitive to the feelings and emotions of others." The CR value for this scale was 0.845, ensuring good reliability.
3. Inclusive Leadership was measured using a 9-item scale developed by Carmeli (2010). This scale assesses leaders' availability and openness to employees' input. A representative item is: "My manager is available for professional questions I would like to consult with him/her (availability)." The scale demonstrated a strong reliability with a CR value of 0.964.
4. Core Self-Evaluations (CSEs) were measured using the Core Self-Evaluations Scale (CSES) developed by Judge et al. (2003), consisting of 12 items. This scale evaluates an individual's fundamental assessments of their capabilities and worth. A sample item includes: "Sometimes, I do not feel in control of my work." The CR of this scale was 0.73, indicating acceptable reliability.
5. Organizational Culture was measured using a 6-item scale from Arinanye (2015). This scale assesses the perceived cultural environment within the organization. A sample statement is: "I am expected to have more individual responsibility for my job performance." The CR for this scale was 0.774, indicating satisfactory reliability.
6. Operational Effectiveness was measured using a 24-item scale developed by Ricardo Santa. This scale evaluates the

organization's ability to maintain consistent and high-quality product and service delivery. A sample item includes: "The organization is looking for a consistent provision of products and services that satisfy customers." The CR for this scale was 0.853, demonstrating good internal consistency.

All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The selection of these scales was based on their established validity and reliability in prior studies,

ensuring robust measurement of the study's constructs.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Data Screening

Data screening has been done with the help of Data collected based on the PLS software. These applications have been used to understand the process of data screening and revealing the results based on the specific operations to understand the value of P and emphasise the limited sample size for retrieving the results of the study.

Table 1: Path coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE -> HAW	0.715	0.711	0.082	8.711	0.000
EI -> CSE	0.487	0.491	0.109	4.466	0.000
EI -> HAW	-0.072	-0.051	0.090	0.806	0.420
EI -> IL	-0.028	-0.035	0.094	0.297	0.766
IL -> OE	0.075	0.062	0.088	0.852	0.394
OC -> IL	0.674	0.680	0.046	14.803	0.000
OC -> OE	0.749	0.751	0.056	13.344	0.000

Notes: Emotional Intelligence (EI), Core Self-Evaluations (CSE), Happiness at Work (HAW), Inclusive Leadership (IL), Operational Effectiveness (OE), Organisational Culture (OC)

OC -> OE value has been found high as compared to other comparisons in the pathway of the p value. The path coefficient value is helpful in reviewing the variance and results based on the data collected from the respondents. The value is significant if the P value is more than 0.05 in most of the results. The data is narrating the value for a lot of uh

variables are taken from the conceptual framework and giving the result. The analytics has been reviewed in the context of various comparisons where the value has been traced low in most of the variables. The dominant result has been traced for the value of OC in contrast to OE only. This shows correlational support in handling the data and ensuring the application of the various analytical support in the context of about 7.51 values for the variable at one place and 7.49 at another place.

Table 2: Outer loading

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE 1 < CSE	0.526	0.514	0.138	3.809	0.000
CSE 10 < CSE	0.190	0.175	0.178	1.068	0.286
CSE 11 < CSE	0.240	0.232	0.131	1.830	0.067
CSE 12 < CSE	0.178	0.160	0.199	0.896	0.370
CSE 2 < CSE	0.417	0.400	0.173	2.410	0.016
CSE 3 < CSE	0.682	0.675	0.100	6.840	0.000
CSE 4 < CSE	0.475	0.451	0.134	3.540	0.000
CSE 5 < CSE	0.368	0.355	0.142	2.585	0.010
CSE 6 < CSE	0.644	0.624	0.107	6.007	0.000
CSE 7 < CSE	0.457	0.442	0.173	2.642	0.008
CSE 8 < CSE	0.571	0.561	0.114	5.007	0.000
CSE 9 < CSE	0.638	0.630	0.082	7.749	0.000
EI 1 < EI	0.784	0.784	0.090	8.691	0.000

EI 2 < EI	0.848	0.835	0.078	10.921	0.000
EI 3 < EI	0.825	0.808	0.080	10.350	0.000
EI 4 < EI	0.426	0.407	0.176	2.420	0.016
HAW 1 < HAW	0.949	0.947	0.011	87.159	0.000
HAW 2 < HAW	0.968	0.968	0.009	104.716	0.000
HAW 3 < HAW	0.930	0.928	0.019	48.439	0.000
HAW 4 < HAW	0.600	0.596	0.083	7.195	0.000
IL 1 < IL	0.838	0.833	0.048	17.488	0.000
IL 2 < IL	0.862	0.861	0.031	28.187	0.000
IL 3 < IL	0.885	0.886	0.022	39.651	0.000
IL 4 < IL	0.946	0.944	0.012	79.459	0.000
IL 5 < IL	0.855	0.855	0.031	27.155	0.000
IL 6 < IL	0.916	0.914	0.020	44.868	0.000
IL 7 < IL	0.822	0.818	0.041	20.272	0.000
IL 8 < IL	0.761	0.756	0.072	10.618	0.000
IL 9 < IL	0.856	0.851	0.036	23.628	0.000
OC 1 < OC	0.381	0.398	0.181	2.113	0.035
OC 10 < OC	0.873	0.866	0.036	24.353	0.000
OC 11 < OC	0.870	0.854	0.055	15.899	0.000
OC 12 < OC	0.581	0.561	0.143	4.054	0.000
OC 13 < OC	0.388	0.366	0.191	2.025	0.043
OC 14 < OC	0.658	0.634	0.121	5.422	0.000
OC 2 < OC	0.199	0.217	0.179	1.111	0.267
OC 3 < OC	0.093	0.099	0.148	0.629	0.529
OC 4 < OC	-0.103	-0.094	0.154	0.667	0.505
OC 5 < OC	0.316	0.332	0.192	1.645	0.100
OC 6 < OC	0.513	0.505	0.086	5.950	0.000
OC 7 < OC	0.712	0.703	0.070	10.202	0.000
OC 8 < OC	0.610	0.596	0.108	5.636	0.000
OC 9 < OC	0.771	0.762	0.054	14.186	0.000
OE 1 < OE	0.919	0.916	0.023	39.347	0.000
OE 2 < OE	0.914	0.909	0.028	33.167	0.000
OE 3 < OE	0.961	0.959	0.011	87.283	0.000
OE 4 < OE	0.966	0.964	0.012	83.153	0.000
OE 5 < OE	0.887	0.882	0.032	27.593	0.000
OE 6 < OE	0.873	0.867	0.042	20.872	0.000

The outer loading value has been reviewed with the help of PLS software and it has been found that the value is helpful in justifying the results for comparison of the direct and indirect variables. It is a showing that if the value is more than 0.7 then it is contributing a construct for validity and can have a significant impact in the research. The table

shows more than 0.7 for most of the variables so it has been justified that maximum variables are showing a dominant context for the potential of significance in Emotional Intelligence (EI) and productivity in the organizational goals achievement. 0.484 low value has been found for OC only at some places.

Table 3: R Square

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE	0.237	0.253	0.096	2.482	0.013
HAW	0.466	0.484	0.077	6.052	0.000
IL	0.447	0.462	0.065	6.926	0.000
OE	0.642	0.637	0.092	7.007	0.000

R square shows the determination coefficient with the variances so discrimination could be

possible between the independent and independent variables based on their

relationship. The value ranges from zero to 1 where the highest possible values give significant relationships as compared to the lower ones. The table shows a higher value for CSE as dominance at 0.237 followed by

OE at 0.642. Explanatory power has been represented for the moderating variables and it has been suggested that the dominant threshold has been traced for CSE with an influence of Emotional Intelligence (EI).

Table 4: R Square Adjustment

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE	0.232	0.248	0.096	2.411	0.016
HAW	0.459	0.476	0.078	5.876	0.000
IL	0.439	0.455	0.065	6.717	0.000
OE	0.637	0.632	0.093	6.859	0.000

The R square variance has been reviewed based on the dependent variables in collaboration with the independent ones. They act as predictors to forecast the outline value and discuss the implementations based on the adjustments of R square variance.

0.232 is giving a dominant value for CSE in collaboration with its implementation however the least value has been traced for HAW. The companion collaboration is showing 2 where CSE remained dominant.

Table 5: RHO c

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE	0.758	0.745	0.040	19.016	0.000
EI	0.822	0.811	0.060	13.644	0.000
HAW	0.927	0.926	0.012	75.771	0.000
IL	0.963	0.962	0.007	129.599	0.000
OC	0.832	0.830	0.019	42.814	0.000
OE	0.971	0.969	0.009	109.809	0.000

RHO c has reviewed the P value for various variables as per conceptual framework and it has been outlined that there is an extreme difference between the lowest and the highest value. The lowest value is traced as 7.580 for

CSE however, the highest one is 129.599 for HAW. It is narrating that director EI has been a dominant concern in CSE handling in the organizations and can be a true game changer while dealing with the challenges.

Table 6: RHO a

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE	0.720	0.736	0.036	20.013	0.000
EI	0.788	0.786	0.113	6.999	0.000
HAW	0.935	0.933	0.021	44.653	0.000
IL	0.970	0.971	0.005	210.356	0.000
OC	0.879	0.881	0.025	35.883	0.000
OE	0.965	0.964	0.010	95.192	0.000

RHO c value has been reviewed in the context of P value variations and it has been found that the maximum Value exists for CSE for about 20.013 while the least value is

for IL which is 0.970. It has been found that the difference between 2 is again high which needs to be addressed with the context of collaboration and contrasts.

Table 7: Average Variance

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values
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				(O/STDEV)	
CSE	0.230	0.239	0.020	11.341	0.000
EI	0.549	0.545	0.051	10.679	0.000
HAW	0.766	0.764	0.029	26.078	0.000
IL	0.742	0.740	0.038	19.726	0.000
OC	0.320	0.329	0.031	10.208	0.000
OE	0.848	0.841	0.039	21.987	0.000

The average variance executes the value for contrast where the amount of the various latent constructs has been outlined to understand the total variance in the findings. It guides the reader about the influence of convergent validity in collaboration to the acceptance of the hypothesis under the privilege of specific values mentioned in the

table. It is showing the lowest value for about 10.208 OC while on the other hand, the highest value has been outlined for HAW as 26.078 and CE as 21.987. The differences justify the correlations and the variances of variables in the current analysis based on the average various execution values.

Table 8: Cronbach Alpha

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CSE	0.680	0.676	0.041	16.525	0.000
EI	0.728	0.726	0.044	16.441	0.000
HAW	0.888	0.886	0.021	42.445	0.000
IL	0.957	0.956	0.008	117.581	0.000
OC	0.793	0.790	0.025	32.053	0.000
OE	0.964	0.961	0.012	83.550	0.000

The Cronbach alpha value is linked with the consistency and reliability factors while measuring the variable. It has been found that the consistency and reliability factor can be high if the value of the ground batch

alpha is above 0.7 with significance. The original sample of the value shows a high value above 0.7 for most of the variables. However, some of the variables like CSE show values below 0.7 which is alarming.

Table 9: HTMT

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EI <-> CSE	0.561	0.605	0.500	0.735
HAW <-> CSE	0.697	0.696	0.607	0.779
HAW <-> EI	0.331	0.356	0.183	0.559
IL <-> CSE	0.696	0.702	0.623	0.774
IL <-> EI	0.214	0.257	0.132	0.456
IL <-> HAW	0.419	0.411	0.202	0.600
OC <-> CSE	0.930	0.937	0.867	1.003
OC <-> EI	0.514	0.564	0.434	0.726
OC <-> HAW	0.753	0.749	0.651	0.833
OC <-> IL	0.684	0.685	0.593	0.764
OE <-> CSE	0.672	0.675	0.584	0.755
OE <-> EI	0.321	0.349	0.122	0.669
OE <-> HAW	0.646	0.631	0.428	0.778
OE <-> IL	0.579	0.568	0.359	0.723
OE <-> OC	0.782	0.773	0.658	0.855

HTMT follows the pattern of discriminant validity in collaboration to construct That allows the correlational support in

understanding the discrimination and discriminant validity for the variables. The value has been contrasted and checked that if

it is above 0.7 then it can be influencing which has been reviewed for the contrast of two variables if sequentially. It has been found that the value has been placed above 0.7 for some of the variables however CSE has been traced to below again when it is contrasted with IL and EI is also found low for IL. HAW Value has been traced as low for most of the variables in collaboration which is showing alarming feedback that the HAW has been under the influence of negative output.

Statistical Review

Statistical techniques are applied to reveal the results, they include HTMT, Cronbach alpha, P values finding, path coefficients, outer loading, R adjustments reliance values and some others. Smart PLS has helped the researcher to implement these statistical techniques using skilled efforts on a smart and small sample size of 150. Smart PLS supports the data analysis process because a small set can be analysed with the help of smart PLS software where complex models ideally support the quantitative analysis by predictive modelling in non-normal data. The statistical operations of R values have helped the researcher to explore the dependent variables' variance in collaboration with the potential predictive capability (Carpenter, 2017). It has ideally implemented the statistical operations to understand how the path coefficient value can be comprehensive for understanding the significance of variables and their Co relationship with other variables of the study. Use of the statistical analysis has guided the researcher in handling complex models and making sure that relevant operations are helpful in releasing the correct output.

HTMT value has been reviewed to discriminate validity using the threshold of 0.85 and above for most of the variables. It is guiding the researcher about the use of a discriminate validity for finding the answers and understanding the intensity of output. Statistical operations of our adjustment value and Cronbach alpha are also helpful in supporting the evidence-based output where the researcher is able to test the hypothesis based on the data collected and aligned with

the support of dividends from the results of the study. The hypothesis of the study is about 12 which seems a huge sum based on the results collected from a small sample of 150 samples from the whole population. Here the statistical operations have helped the researcher to deal with the hypothetical testing process using theory-based evidence and make sure that software applications are able to keep a balance between indication of internal and external consistency based on the software results of a smart PLS (Garavan et al., 2012).

Hypotheses Testing

This study is performed to review the impact of HR analytics on talent management and organization creativity in the garment industry in Pakistan. It has been analysed using sixteen hypotheses in reference to some opinions like, according to Thukral, E. (2021), the global economy is increasingly characterized by **volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity**. The study has supported the evidence based on factors such as **economic recessions, geopolitical instability, trade wars, pandemics, and climate change** introduce significant unpredictability into business operations to generate the variables. The questionnaire has been based on the review support from the researcher where the idea has been explored using relevant opinions based on the data outlined for the study. The researcher is able to test the hypotheses based on the outlined plan of the study using skilled support of the variables of the analysis (Collings & Mellahi, 2009).

H1: Employees' emotional intelligence is positively related to happiness at work.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is widely recognized as a key determinant of workplace happiness. Studies have consistently shown that individuals with high EI experience greater job satisfaction, emotional well-being, and overall happiness at work. EI enables employees to better understand and regulate their emotions, which contributes to healthier interpersonal relationships and a more positive work environment. For example, research by Nguyen et al. (2018)

demonstrated a significant positive relationship between EI and workplace happiness across various industries, emphasizing that employees with high EI are more adept at managing stress and fostering harmonious relationships with colleagues. A meta-analysis by Joseph and Newman (2010) concluded that EI positively correlates with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. They argued that emotionally intelligent individuals are more likely to interpret workplace challenges constructively, reducing the negative impact of stressors. For instance, in a study conducted among educators, emotional intelligence was found to mediate the relationship between job stress and burnout, enhancing overall workplace happiness.

In Pakistan, Shafique et al. (2019) studied the relationship between EI and job satisfaction among healthcare professionals. Their findings revealed a significant positive correlation, suggesting that emotionally intelligent individuals were more likely to experience job satisfaction and reduced stress levels. Similarly, a study by Rehman and Karim (2021) in Pakistan's banking sector found that EI played a crucial role in enhancing workplace happiness by improving interpersonal communication and emotional regulation. However, most of these studies focus on service-oriented industries. By studying this relationship in Karachi's garment manufacturing sector, this research seeks to fill this gap and test the hypothesis:

H2: Employee emotional intelligence is positively related to core self-evaluations.

This study addresses this limitation by examining the impact of EI on CSEs in Karachi's garment sector. Core self-evaluations (CSEs) refer to an individual's fundamental assessment of their worth and capabilities, encompassing traits such as self-esteem, self-efficacy, emotional stability, and locus of control. Studies indicate a strong positive relationship between EI and CSEs, as emotionally intelligent individuals tend to exhibit greater self-awareness and self-confidence. Emotional regulation, a core component of EI, enables individuals to maintain emotional stability and a positive

outlook, which directly enhances their self-evaluations.

Nguyen et al. (2020) highlighted that employees with higher EI reported better CSEs, which in turn contributed to greater resilience and job satisfaction. Their findings underscore that emotionally intelligent individuals possess greater self-belief and confidence, leading to more effective coping mechanisms. For instance, a study by Adeyemo (2007) revealed that EI significantly predicted self-efficacy among teachers, further reinforcing the link between emotional intelligence and core self-evaluations. In Pakistan, Bukhari and Ali (2017) examined the relationship between EI and self-efficacy among university students and found a significant positive association. Their study highlighted that individuals with higher EI were better equipped to handle academic stress and maintain a positive self-concept. While these findings provide insights into the educational sector, limited evidence exists for labor-intensive industries.

H3: Core self-evaluations are positively related to happiness at work for employees.

Core self-evaluations have been extensively linked to workplace happiness. Employees with positive CSEs are more likely to exhibit confidence, resilience, and optimism, which contribute to their overall happiness and job satisfaction. Research by Lopez & Garcia (2019) confirmed that individuals with higher CSEs tend to view their work as more meaningful and fulfilling, fostering greater engagement and emotional well-being. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2021) found that core self-evaluations significantly predict happiness at work by enabling employees to cope better with workplace stressors. In addition, positive CSEs are associated with improved adaptability to workplace changes and challenges. For example, in a longitudinal study conducted by Bono and Judge (2003), individuals with higher CSEs demonstrated greater resilience to organizational restructuring and role transitions, maintaining their job satisfaction levels. In Pakistan, Khan et al. (2020) explored the role of CSEs in predicting job satisfaction among teachers and found that

higher self-evaluations were significantly associated with improved emotional well-being and workplace happiness. Although these studies highlight the relevance of CSEs, further research is needed in industries like garment manufacturing.

H4: Employees' emotional intelligence positively impacts inclusive leadership.

Inclusive leadership emphasizes fairness, equity, and respect for diverse perspectives within the workplace. Emotional intelligence is considered a critical enabler of inclusive leadership, as it equips leaders with the skills to navigate complex social dynamics, foster collaboration, and create psychologically safe environments. Gupta et al. (2020) found that leaders with high EI are more likely to demonstrate inclusive behaviors, such as active listening and empathy, which enhance team performance and employee satisfaction. A study by Carmeli et al. (2010) highlighted that emotionally intelligent leaders foster stronger bonds with their teams by understanding individual needs and preferences, thereby promoting inclusivity. These findings have been corroborated in the context of multinational corporations, where inclusive leadership was linked to higher team cohesion and reduced turnover intentions. In Pakistan, Iqbal and Mahmood (2021) investigated the role of EI in fostering inclusive leadership in higher education institutions and found significant positive effects on team collaboration and employee morale.

H5: Inclusive leadership positively impacts operational effectiveness.

This research extends these insights by focusing on Karachi's garment sector. Operational effectiveness refers to the ability of an organization to deliver products or services efficiently while maintaining high standards of quality and productivity. Inclusive leadership plays a pivotal role in achieving operational effectiveness by fostering collaboration, innovation, and employee engagement. Research by Kearney and Gebert (2009) demonstrated that inclusive leadership enhances team performance and decision-making by

encouraging diverse perspectives and leveraging the strengths of all team members. In the manufacturing sector, studies have highlighted the significance of inclusive leadership in improving operational metrics. For instance, Carmeli et al. (2010) found that teams led by inclusive leaders exhibited higher levels of productivity and quality assurance. These leaders created environments where employees felt valued and motivated to contribute their best efforts. Similarly, a study by Shore et al. (2011) emphasized that inclusive leadership reduces workplace conflicts and enhances operational efficiency by fostering mutual respect and trust. In Pakistan, Ahmed et al. (2020) examined the relationship between inclusive leadership and operational outcomes in the textile industry. Their findings revealed that inclusive leaders positively influenced team cohesion and workflow efficiency, leading to better operational performance.

H6: Organizational culture moderates the relationship between inclusive leadership and job performance.

This study aims to address this gap by examining the moderating role of organizational culture in Karachi's garment sector. Organizational culture shapes the behaviors, attitudes, and outcomes of employees, acting as a powerful moderator in workplace dynamics. Schein (2010) emphasized that a supportive culture amplifies the effectiveness of inclusive leadership by fostering collaboration and trust. In diverse teams, inclusive leadership is more impactful in cultures that prioritize openness and respect for differences. Studies by Chen & Wang (2020) highlight that in cultures lacking inclusivity, the positive effects of inclusive leadership on employee performance are diminished. Organizational culture also moderates the influence of emotional intelligence on operational outcomes. For instance, Gelfand et al. (2007) found that in hierarchical cultures, employees with high EI were better able to navigate power dynamics, leading to enhanced team performance. In Pakistan, Ahmed and Saeed (2019) examined the moderating role of organizational culture in the banking sector

and found that cultures promoting innovation and openness significantly enhanced the relationship between leadership and employee performance. Despite these insights, there is limited

empirical evidence on how organizational culture moderate's leadership outcomes in labor-intensive industries like garment manufacturing.

Figure 2: Diagrammatic review of hypothesis (Author)

The conceptual framework has been previously outlined which is helpful for the researcher to reveal how the link has been developed between various points on the hypothetical approaches and how the variables are in collaboration with one another. HR analytics has taken the medal position by taking the connectivity from technological context, organizational context and environmental context. All the 3 agents are influencing HR analytics directly because they have been studied for an impact on HR analytics in the paradigm of becoming a game changer in organizations in the modern era of applications. The impact has been reviewed for talent management, organizational creativity and human resource management activities by understanding how human resource analytics has influenced these critical areas. The collaboration has been judgmentally studied with the help of 16 hypotheses in sequence. The author is able to develop the connection between all the hypotheses by understanding their applications and making sure that how they have an influential potential while

connectivity has been checked with the help of relevant hypothetical applications.

CONCLUSION

Emotional skills are a topic that is strongly present in our society. Their development is considered important and even trendy. However, it is noteworthy that the need to develop emotional skills is generally associated with children and young people. In different parts of Pakistan, children's emotional skills instructor training and various children's emotional skills groups are available, which are based on the development of the trainee's own emotional skills, but the main emphasis is almost without exception placed on the customer (Wöcke et al., 2007). Society's investment in emotional skills is reflected in some aspects in the early childhood education plans of daycare centers and school curricula. The phenomenon of strongly associating the need to develop emotional skills with children and young people is also reflected in the topic choices of studies conducted on the subject. Emotional intelligence research on employees in Pakistan has so far focused almost

exclusively on the business world. This has proven that this meta-skill is directly proportional to success and well-being at work, both at the level of managers and white-collar employees. Most literature related to emotional skills is found in the form of so-called self-help literature, or life skills guides. However, only a fraction of people read books like this. There is still a long way to go before guides and books find their way into workplaces and are read by everyone. The values of the guide we created included an idea that we hope will be true everywhere in the future. Developing emotional skills is the personal responsibility of every employee in the human relations field, and attention must be paid to this already during training (Alonderiene & Majauskaite, 2016).

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